

LINGUOCULTUROLOGY AS AN INTERDISCIPLINARY FIELD: LANGUAGE, CULTURE, AND WORLDVIEW

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Abstract

The article examines linguoculturology as an interdisciplinary field integrating linguistics and cultural studies. The aim is to analyze the interaction between language and culture, their role in shaping worldview, and the mechanisms of cultural transmission. The study applies descriptive, comparative, and linguoculturological methods. The results demonstrate the central role of language in preserving and transmitting cultural meanings. The novelty lies in the comprehensive analysis of conceptual, linguistic, and national worldviews. The practical significance is determined by its relevance for intercultural communication and education.

Keywords

linguoculturology, language and culture, worldview, linguocultureme, intercultural communication

All linguistics is permeated with cultural-historical content, since its subject is language, which constitutes the condition, foundation, and product of culture. Language is not only connected with culture; it grows out of it and expresses it. Language functions both as an instrument for the creation, development, and preservation of culture, and as its component. Linguoculturology studies these processes at the intersection of linguistics and cultural studies.

Language and culture are fundamental categories of linguoculturology. There exists a direct relationship between language, culture, and thinking. Language performs communicative, cumulative, and directive functions, shaping both individual consciousness and collective worldview.

One of the key notions of linguoculturology is the concept of worldview, including conceptual, linguistic, and national types. The conceptual worldview is based on cognition, while the linguistic worldview reflects knowledge through language structures. The national worldview represents stable cultural patterns reflected in behavior, traditions, and speech.

The linguocultureme is the fundamental unit of analysis, combining linguistic meaning and cultural sense. It reflects the unity of language and culture and carries connotative meaning within a specific cultural context.

Modern linguoculturology integrates interdisciplinary approaches, including cognitive linguistics, anthropology, and discourse analysis. It also studies linguistic personality as a bearer of cultural and linguistic knowledge.

In the conditions of globalization, linguoculturology plays a crucial role in intercultural communication. It helps overcome cultural barriers and promotes mutual understanding between different cultures.

Thus, linguoculturology explains how language preserves, transmits, and transforms cultural values and meanings in communication processes.

Linguoculturology is generally considered to have emerged in the last quarter of the twentieth century as a result of the anthropological paradigm in linguistics. However, its

theoretical foundations were laid in the nineteenth century by W. von Humboldt, who established the relationship between language and the character of a people.

According to Humboldt, language creates an intermediate world between human beings and reality. Thus, the study of a foreign language is not merely the acquisition of linguistic competence but also the acquisition of a new worldview.

Language and culture are the fundamental categories of linguoculturology. There exists a direct relationship between language, culture, and thinking: culture represents content, while language serves as the form of its expression. Language performs several key functions, including communicative, cumulative, and directive functions.

The aim of linguoculturology is to study the ways in which language embodies, preserves, and transmits culture within its units. The object of study is the interaction between language, culture, and the human being as a bearer of both.

This discipline is situated at the intersection of linguistics, cultural studies, ethnography, and psycholinguistics. It examines not only language as a system but also real communicative processes, including the relationship between linguistic expressions and the mentality, traditions, and customs of a people.

One of the key concepts of linguoculturology is the notion of the worldview. In general terms, it is understood as an ordered system of knowledge about reality formed in human consciousness.

It is essential to distinguish between three types of worldview:

conceptual worldview

linguistic worldview

national worldview

The conceptual worldview is the result of cognitive activity and is based on structured knowledge (the conceptsphere)

The linguistic worldview reflects this knowledge through language and represents the “world in the mirror of language.”

The national worldview, in turn, reflects stable and recurring features common to a particular culture. It manifests itself in behavior, speech, traditions, and collective consciousness, including proverbs, sayings, and stereotypes. Language expresses the specific features of national mentality and serves as a mechanism that reveals human consciousness.

At present, in linguistics, alongside the concepts of the conceptual and linguistic worldviews, the notion of the national worldview has also become established. The national worldview represents what is common, stable, and recurring in the worldviews of individual members of a nation. In this regard, the national worldview is, on the one hand, an abstraction, and on the other, a cognitive-psychological reality manifested in the intellectual and cognitive activity of a people, as well as in their physical and verbal behavior. The national worldview is revealed in the uniformity of a people’s behavior in stereotypical situations, in their shared perceptions of reality, in statements and “common opinions,” in judgments about reality, and in proverbs, sayings, and aphorisms (Sternin, 2000), since language is an integral part of culture and its instrument; it is the reality of our spirit, the face of culture. It expresses, in an explicit form, the specific features of national mentality. Language is a mechanism that has opened up the realm of consciousness to humans (Zhinkin, 1998: 56).

V.V. Vorobyev considers the main unit of linguocultural analysis to be the linguocultureme, defined as a “dialectical unity of linguistic and extralinguistic (conceptual and referential) content” (Vorobyev, 1997: 45). Unlike a word, a linguocultureme has a more complex structure: its content plane is divided into linguistic meaning and cultural sense. A linguocultureme possesses a connotative meaning and “exists as long as the ideological context that generated it remains alive” (Vorobyev, 1997: 52).

Thus, linguoculturology is a linguistic discipline that studies material and spiritual culture as embodied in a living national language and manifested in linguistic processes (Oparina, 1999). It makes it possible to identify and explain how one of the fundamental functions of language is carried out—namely, to serve as a tool for the creation, development, preservation, and transmission of culture.

Conclusion

Linguoculturology is an interdisciplinary field that studies the interaction between language and culture. It contributes to deeper understanding of worldview, cultural identity, and communication processes in modern society. The concept of the national worldview plays a significant role in modern linguistics, reflecting the shared cognitive and cultural patterns of a people. Language, as an integral part of culture, serves not only as a means of communication but also as a tool for preserving and transmitting cultural values and national mentality. The notion of the linguocultureme highlights the deep connection between linguistic meaning and cultural context, demonstrating that language units carry both semantic and cultural significance. Therefore, linguoculturology provides an essential framework for understanding the interaction between language and culture.

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